

The Holistic Approach of the Literary Symbol in Dimitrie Anghel's Poetry

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ABSTRACT: For the first time, Aristotle synthesised, in his *Metaphysics*, the holistic principle, in a specific way, sustaining the idea that a system's properties cannot be determined or explained individually by each of its parts, but the system, as a whole, determines how its parts would act. The holistic approach of literary symbols implies the change of the attitude in order to facilitate the comprehension, and to discover things in a more optimistic process, holding back the pessimistic view of things. The human being in relation with itself, with the society and the universe, has a unique manner of exhibition recorded in modern cognitive psychology, and sometimes manifested in literature. C. G. Jung's concept of "collective unconscious" implied a bond between the individual and humanity as a whole; the representation of an idea that becomes a symbol of a universal acceptance.

KEY WORDS: literature, consciousness, ideas, poem, symbol

For the first time, Aristotle synthesised in his *Metaphysics* the holistic principle in a specific way: "An entire is more than the sum of its parts." It sustains the idea that a system's properties cannot be determined or explained individually by each of its parts, but the system, as a whole, determines how its parts would act.

The holistic approach implies achieving an emotional goal: the change of the attitude in order to facilitate the comprehension and

to discover things in a more optimistic process, holding back the pessimistic view of things.

The human being in relation with itself, with the society and the universe, has a unique manner of exhibition recorded in modern cognitive psychology, and sometimes manifested in literature. Jung tried to understand the human psychic in its whole according to its relationships with others. Thus, its concept of collective unconscious implied a bond between the individual and humanity as a whole. So, the representation of an idea becomes a symbol of a universal acceptance.

Most of the time incursions into diverse areas as ethnography, philosophy, psychoanalysis, linguistics, rhetoric, aesthetics and poetics are taken in order to understand the connection literature–symbol given that literature seems inextricably linked to the idea of a symbol. But the problem is that the literary symbol has not been sufficiently or satisfactorily yet theorised despite multidisciplinary character of researches in the field of poetry.

Originally, the symbol represents the sign of an ontological, analogical or conventional connection. Furthermore, the evolution of language, the symbolic relations have become increasingly complex. The symbol offers to the sensitivity, sensitive or intelligible realities so that the submitted idea—cannot be accounted for in a different way—it remains eternally active.

Together with the devoted symbols (now conventional) it also appears the contingent symbols (according to the name given by Henri Morier) created by the writer who gives a symbolic value to the object, being or circumstance. This function of the poetic language is programmatic used by symbolism/the symbolist poets for which the poetic symbol becomes a substitute for the absolute truth.

Besides the advent of psychoanalysis, symbolic interpretation of oneiric experiences has been used, the symbol appearing subconsciously. In Sigmund Freud's conception, any symbol is a representation of a repressed experience, censored by super-ego, which could not have in this way a form of direct expression, but only ciphered.

Frequently, we encounter in Dimitrie Anghel's poetic work numerous symbols, enciphers of inner states, most revolving around

the concept of “flower” (although not always mentioned this word), especially in the targeted volume, “In the garden”/“In gradina.” There are mentioned here many kinds of flowers, from the “noble” ones as the rose, the lily to the common ones and considered by other writers insignificant—the marjoram, the goldenseal, the basil—totalling 40 different names of flowers encountered by their colour in its system of representations. The poet cultivates the artificial nature environment, humanised by the gardens and the process of synaesthesia. He is a contemplative person, a dreamer who brings the theme of travels in poetry, the theme of evasion, bohemian motif and images of the marine landscape. The symbolism in his poetry is combined with romantic notes.

Starting from the poem that opens the homonymous volume the symbol of garden has been detached (symbol of its system of correspondence and images) in different meanings: the garden—the legendary park, the garden—the temple (The garden is a grape sweet—“Melancholy”), the garden—a place of mystery in which sweet spells are included (“flowers”). In the garden, stories and legends are taken place in the centre of which they are either plant through the flowers carefully chosen, or nymphs, vestals, deities and legendary figures as rolled down from Olympus (Elysium fields, Elsenaur, Hamlet, Oleander, Hera, Ofelia)—exotic elements carried out from aboriginal. In Dimitrie Anghel’s poetry the garden is a miniature world, the cosmos, the heavenly earth and it is populated by a wide range of plants.

The man exercising his power over tamed nature and in the centre of the garden is THE FLOWER that returns frequently as a literary motif in various forms. The flower embodies the spiritual perfection bringing together the virtues of the soul, the edenic state obtained through love and harmony. The flowers are divided into *feeble, mallow lily-of-the-valley, autumn, shadow, true, field flowers*; sometimes *they die melted by dreaming or they are sad*—the favourite personified epithet of the poet.

The poet does not seem to have any preference for a particular type of flower, but THE ROSE with *its leaves of wax* is remarkable or the one with *white diaphanous¹ petals falling down*, totalling the inner feelings, love, self-awareness and, at the same time, the

regeneration and the initiation into the mysteries, rarely extinction by wilting—*rose dying*.²

The passionate and steadfast love, safety is symbolised by THE BASIL—a plant that has been ignored by other poets. This also symbolizes the solar spell of the Romanian village in the sense of folk belief, purification that has to do with the holy water of baptism with a strong ancestral anchor, as the powerful olfactory inflections such as the lily, embalming the whole space of the garden where *the flowers are fighting* and *the only winner until now reigns the basil*.³ The olfactory is concerned by fierce competition—*many of them compete to win or die in battle*⁴ being involved *the naive wrath of flowers* and lily and the jasmine, *the proud verbenas, a broken mallow* under the seal of the night *suddenly it smells of love and death*.⁵

The noble, predominantly white LILY symbolises pure and innocent love, wearing *a royal mantle*,⁶ it is the flower of glory and also the flower of death, likened with the sacred chalice, encompassing the bliss that leads to oblivion under its narcotic power—after the rain *the lilies wake up in the shade, shedding their profane breeze*.⁷ In the same register *as by a charm*, its power is overwhelming: *And under the sign made by the lily (...) each of them/a leave is shaken in the wind—and the wind has left the garden*,⁸ in this way managing the freedom of the other flowers under the tyranny of winter. The lily once symbolised the light and the masculine principle.

The light in Anghel's poems is WHITE and strong. The mallow flowers are also white or *white flowers of lily-of-the-valley* next to a *light face* and a *ghostly white hand* dominated by the light with *silver butterflies*⁹ mirrored under the tutelage of jasmine perfume—and this being a pure white. White is also represented by *snowflakes*,¹⁰ *canvas as white as the snow*.¹¹ White is not attributed only to the flowers but also to the mists, the oxymoron: *white mists* personified—they were *sleeping piles of defeated sleep; of the white mist bands, with their white wings* that they *were lost the silent night*¹² (in a regal of personifications and metaphors in ample visual images).

The SUN is associated with white and light as a multi-faceted entity, it is also the manifestation of divinity. It is the source of light, heat and of life and immortality. Although *grieved* is a *good sweet brother*, offering *the last kiss*. It is the life force of the universe, it

represents the good and it is metaphorically surprised *the golden nest* and *the sweet yellow's glow*.¹³ The ubiquitous symbol, the garden, comes under the protective sun.

THE TWILIGHT brings into existence the atmosphere of dusk creating the image before carrying out the achievement of a miracle, it announces the great journey and it introduces the death with the feelings of melancholy and nostalgia, it is a trigger of reveries and nostalgic beauty of the exterior and also the interior, inner decline.

The only spot of colour seen in the poem "In the Garden" is provided by the appearance of *leaf wax* roses and of the carnation that remains stuck to the soul *like a drop of blood*,¹⁴ the organic interpenetration of an *animus* with an *anima*. From the poem's opening volume thus, the unprecedented comparison introduces, the ardour and the beauty, symbolism of *red* rosy played by an impressive force in *a world enriched by roses*.¹⁵ The same colour is reproduced indirectly by the appearance of the precious stone which is compared with the flower—*a goldenseal like a ruby*¹⁶ or *rose* with its superabundant petals . . . *like blood splatter*,¹⁷ *the pale woodbine is bloody*,¹⁸ emphasising the idea of lust and passion.

The entire chromatic first volume of poems is concentrated on the expressive power of the RAINBOW that meets an overwhelming frequency: *lights of rainbows are thrown from the sky*,¹⁹ *Sun rainbows*²⁰ with its contribution to the musicality through its symbolism: the seven colours are identified with the seven musical notes, the contrast of its composition and the adverse colours warns about the human being inherent dualism. The rainbow animates the materiality of the world and raises awareness.

THE SUNFLOWER is associated with THE LIGHT whom the sun *sent its thoughts on the last kiss*. The lack of light suggests extinction—*How difficult must be the sleep in the dust of hillocks*.²¹ So the sleep motif induces the idea of crossing the timelessness and the dissolving of any states of suffering leading to a spiritual inertia.

The death of flowers is frequently: *marjorams' death—and now they fade away*,²² *the autumn flowers*²³ *fade away, too, grieved flowers fade away, a rose was fading away*,²⁴ *the life of faded away queens*,²⁵ *life would have died defeated by melancholy*.²⁶ The sleep also refers to extinction, the death being the daughter of the night and the sister

of the sleep. This is achieved by *hovering the darkness of the night sweet and full of mysteries*.²⁷ Olfactory images are interwoven with the visual ones in the harmony of an ineffable atmosphere. Under the power of the night there are manifested the doubt, the uncertainty and the yearning for transcendence of the human being with all its intricacies who does not reveal itself, keeping the mystery.

In the garden associated with the hermitage, the death triumphs generating a disarming hypothesis: *life would have died defeated by melancholy*²⁸ like a rosa at Elseneur which passed away peacefully. It can be defied with *the fire of your mouth to revive the stream of dead waters*, but the feeling is desolated *because the death is everywhere and the death is forever silent*.²⁹

In the garden of Luxembourg, *ancient and precious STATUES* appear as a representation of steadiness feelings by petrifying of the happy moment to be enjoyed: *dearest you and me* in contrast to the transience of human being that surprises the missing queens *astonished in the cold stone by a poor perishable hand*.³⁰ The first material of the statues suggests the steadfastness of feelings the dismayed poet has been aspiring surprised by the contrast of oxymoron: *the eternal romance elapsed, / born from a kiss and dead after ten days*. But the intensity of inner feeling makes all the effort to be rated or any other subsequent suffering: *who wouldn't want to live again those moments?* The inexorable transience focuses in a remarkable structure: *the time was bewildered flowing*³¹ all that can be kept is the memory—*years and years have passed away. . .*³² *Eternal in this world are only wreathes of laurel leaves*.³³ The laurel is a plant of immortality and emblem of glory, evergreen; it is a symbol of soul immortality.

The calm and friendly atmosphere is caught, most of the times at night when the fairy is accentuated at the highest levels: *A sweet night chased away from a seraglio, by an odalisque*³⁴ in suggestive text from its title—“A night charm”/“Farmec de noapte”—where the novelty of the metaphor induces the mystery state: *shaded flower in the enchanted night where the beats of the wings let their flight in depths*.³⁵

THE BIRD with its flight determines the relationship between earthly and celestial elements, but at the same time the means

by which the soul is escaping from the body, even the instability or failure of acquiring certainties—*huge birds sleeping with wide wings*³⁶ under *the pale sky, in the silent night*.³⁷ The dove, symbol of peace, takes care of flora: *it seemed that the entire garden is given to them to be guarded*.³⁸

The contrast night/dark is frequently met—the light with its potentiating role of oneiric.

The night is the mystery far from the manifestation of demonic; the longing for transcendence located in the depths of human concealment places. The night is associated with black—peer of whites and its opposite, it has been sending to a permanent loss of hope, to the anguish and to the collapse into nothingness, to the original chaos that seems to identify human being at one time. It expects the passivity which is sometimes wanted to be sweetened by reducing, in a unique combination with white (*white mists*).

Often THE EYE which comprises the light and sees towards emphasising the idea of sincere feeling, it is the ability of spiritual perception and it is associated with gods. There are *eyes that cry in the night*,³⁹ *the most carried away- eyes by dreams*.⁴⁰

THE DREAM encodes the ideals and individualises, being also means of transcendence. Associated to *sleep* it is a technique of escaping from routine, a projection of unspoken desires, it is the work of the spirit to a new realm of complete freedom and it requires the privacy of the consciousness, especially in “A Night Charm”/“Farmec de noapte.”

THE WIND is looming as a disturbing factor that brings inconsistency and triggers uncontrolled energies *the song frozen by high wind*. It is *an icy high wind*⁴¹ violent and blind that destabilises the thoughts of the human being. It could also be gentle and regulator of cosmic balance and moral as in “Swap of news”/“Schimb de vești” when spring brings, sometimes it sifts *dust of flowers* and it relaxes the atmosphere—*and nevertheless the garden is cheerful*.⁴² The wind is a manifestation of the divine; it is the spirit or the spiritual influx.

Additionally, the changing/the reinstalling of the season brings GREEN prevailing in any flower throughout the garden. It introduces the hope because the death turns out not to be for good, but it

refers to the possibility of resurrection, rebirth; sacrifice and love, optimism and eternal love.

Rarely, the precious RAIN is seen in the garden: *the tear of rain, like a diamond lit by a ray*⁴³ like the intellectual fertility likened to a gift from the gods.

THE WATER itself is the origin of life and a way of the purification, a centre of regeneration, fertility but also wisdom and virtue. Traditionally it is the origin of creation, the generator of life and death. We retrieve it in *the tear* (it is a testimony of pain and intercession, an uninterrupted flow of the water of soul, identified as lily-of-the-valley), in the rain, in the spring, into the fountain and into the pool—eye water of the garden. Oleander blooms near the pool where *the water refreshes for a moment; it has been renewing its mirror in the moon*.⁴⁴ THE FOUNTAIN embodies the eternal youth, life, immortality or perpetual rejuvenation, regeneration and purification, learning.

The reflection is the MOON, the seclusion space of happy souls; it is the feminine principle which transforms reality. It identifies itself to the essential element of the cosmos, the eye of the universe, a gate to the inner world, to experience artistic feeling, rhythmically repeating life—*it is the holy Moon, a travelling wheel*⁴⁵ invoked in “The curse of the mother”/“Blestem de mamă.”

The mystery is supported by the presence of the Virgin that has not been revealed. There are mentioned mythological figures such as Ariadne, Hera, Ofelia, Narcissus, Elseneur, to the Vestals or courtesans related to their symbolism, along with personification of flowers in the whole Dimitrie Anghel's lyric.

The olfactory is filled by the presence of jasmine, basil, lily, lily-of-the-valley (and form Lily-of-the-valley), rose—*sorrowful smell of roses*—images charged stylistically.

The visual is crowned by rainbows.

The musical instruments are added to the symbols complementing the sonority of lyrics. We meet the brass bands and the drumming in the Parisian context, and the lyre is mentioned in the garden where silence reigns and *where peace grows funereally* then *the silent wind/Like a slumbering hand on the broken string of a lyre*.⁴⁶ The silence is disturbed by the noise of fanfares *sounding*

*a horrid long noise over plane trees; in the desert of the garden the night is announced by a drum–distant that sounded like after battle.*⁴⁷

The reflecting of the two worlds (human and vegetable) one in the other one is performed using the omniscient MIRROR: *Near the tired mirrors, a shaky and pale girl/turns flowers in the pots, as pious as a vestal./... If it had a mouth to speak, the mirror would say many*⁴⁸. This reveals as a small universe in which the poet finds peace, harmony and balance referring to his own childhood, the utopian parallel universe. It symbolises a replica of reality where the ego can watch its true essence or may geminate itself. It involves the self–knowledge, wisdom and prudence.

The theme of these texts is based on the fairy created by fine smells of flowers and it represents an echo of the mallarmean symbol by Samain.

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NOTES

- ¹ 1 Dimitrie Anghel, *Poezii și proză*. (București: Editura Andreas Print, 2010), 18.
- ² Ibid, 25.
- ³ Ibid, 11.
- ⁴ Ibid, 12.
- ⁵ Ibid.
- ⁶ Ibid, 7.
- ⁷ Ibid, 12.
- ⁸ Ibid, 25.
- ⁹ Ibid, 6.
- ¹⁰ Ibid, 24.
- ¹¹ Ibid, 17.
- ¹² Ibid, 21.
- ¹³ Ibid, 10.
- ¹⁴ Ibid, 6.
- ¹⁵ Ibid, 7.
- ¹⁶ Ibid, 8.
- ¹⁷ Ibid, 25.
- ¹⁸ Ibid, 9.
- ¹⁹ Ibid, 8.
- ²⁰ Ibid, 14.
- ²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid, 8.

²³ Ibid, 10.

²⁴ Ibid, 12.

²⁵ Ibid, 16.

²⁶ Ibid, 18.

²⁷ Ibid, 11.

²⁸ Ibid, 19.

²⁹ Ibid, 23.

³⁰ Ibid, 16.

³¹ Ibid, 17.

³² Ibid, 14.

³³ Ibid, 27.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid, 18.

³⁶ Ibid, 21.

³⁷ Ibid, 19.

³⁸ Ibid, 16.

³⁹ Ibid, 15.

⁴⁰ Ibid, 17.

⁴¹ Ibid, 23.

⁴² Ibid, 15.

⁴³ Ibid, 16.

⁴⁴ Ibid, 20.

⁴⁵ Ibid, 28.

⁴⁶ Ibid, 19.

⁴⁷ Ibid. 17.

⁴⁸ E. Dorcescu, (*Poetica non-imanenței*. Semănătorul București: Editura online, 2008), 10.